

THE IMPORTANCE OF THE DIGITAL INFORMATION SPACE IN THE SOCIAL SPACE.

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Abstract: Today, the widespread use of the Internet and information and communication technologies in the world is one of the most important conditions for the socio-economic and cultural development of society, this process is reflected in the formation of a new direction of socio-cultural dynamics. The rapid development of information and communication technologies has led to a further expansion of the types of human activity. With the formation of the digital space, social relations have developed rapidly in it, including such transformational processes as a moral worldview, self-promotion and self-identification, and the perception of moral and philosophical reality by the individual. Nowadays, it is becoming necessary to study such phenomena as axiological paradigms, moral criteria and norms, communication methods, and rapid and sharp changes in views in the digital information space.

Keywords: digital space, information space as a social space, cyberethics, virtual world, etosphere.

Information is the main resource today, changing the world and enabling it to develop. Searching for information has become very simple, and by connecting to the Internet, a person can find any information. Today, the importance of studying cyberspace is reflected in the concepts of virtual world, digital information space, information space, media space that are emerging as a result of the rapid development of the Internet. One of the first types of them is the digital information space, which is defined as follows.

The digital information space is a special virtual world where information is created, transmitted and consumed. The concept of the information space allows us to understand how the modern digital world works. The creation of the information space itself occurred automatically, but information was not exchanged and collected. Many experts believe that there is no clear definition of this phenomenon, while philosophers define it as a world of names and nouns. Belarusian scientists Yakushenko and Shimanskaya drew attention to the fact that the modern world is entering the era of a post-industrial digital economy, and the development of the information sphere, mass media and communications, the problems associated with the use of the modern digital

information space for economic development and the stabilization of social progress are coming to the fore. It is not always possible to clearly define the essence of a given space, but it nevertheless provides information for reflection. Due to the rapid development of transformational processes in cyberspace, which involves more and more people in this space, the main types of information space: mass information space, corporate information space, collective information space, etc., are becoming the basis for studying its conceptual significance. In particular, examples of mass information space include the Internet, television, radio, and public debates. The main feature of this type is that all information is available here, and anyone can get it. Researcher S. Shirin considers this concept from the perspective of a modern media system and defines it as integrated into the global information space with the help of improved communication systems and information transmission methods, national and cross-border information, during the information revolution, while another Russian scientist S.A. Proskurin says that "The information space is a space where information is created, transmitted and consumed." Undoubtedly, the scientist has in mind a certain limited mass information environment in which information flows are interconnected. The mass information environment also directly affects the corporate information space.

Corporate information space - here the formation of the information space is implemented within the framework of one company, office center, production facility. The Russian philosopher M. Katkova approaches this concept as follows: "The corporate information space is a historically formed, provided with legal guarantees and means, providing maximum accessibility for the consumer, coordinated and structured, geographically close and geographically close form of space." The management delivers information to its employees, they transfer it to the department, and sometimes even take it out of the enterprise. In most cases, corporate information remains closed to outsiders.

The most widespread is the public information space, or it is also called public. It includes websites, news, articles, videos on various services, TV channels and radio stations. Information is public, it is not encrypted, and is used for specific purposes. The main disadvantage of this space is that not all information here is reliable and true, anyone can place it, create it in any way they want. In order to activate this information, collect it and develop it interpersonally, the concepts of virtual world and cyberspace were formed. A virtual world is an artificially created world built through programming based

on computer technology. Virtual worlds are interactive virtual environments designed for users to spend their time, and in their current form, they are mostly presented in the form of online multiplayer games, as well as individual websites where users can express themselves through their own features: a name, a nickname, a photo or an avatar - a graphic or textual representation of themselves.

Digital information is a term used to describe the interconnectedness of digital technology in a space. The term was coined in the first decade of the Internet to refer to the online world as a "separate" world, separate from everyday reality. In cyberspace, people can hide behind false identities, as in the famous film "The New". The term has entered popular culture from science fiction and art. It is currently used by technology strategists, security experts, government, military and industry leaders, and entrepreneurs to describe the domain of the global technological environment. In turn, it refers to the global network of interconnected information technology infrastructures, telecommunications networks, and computer processing systems. Cyberspace is an environment in which individuals communicate with each other to satisfy their needs through computer networks. The term became popular in the 1990s, when the use of the Internet, networks, and digital communications grew rapidly, and with it came the emergence of many new ideas and phenomena around the term cyberspace.

The digital information space is a space of personal information. Each person creates a personal information environment that is created individually by him. A smartphone contains many photos, notes, phone numbers and numbers, programs and mobile applications with various information. Personal information, as a rule, does not go beyond the boundaries of a specific device. Based on the above concepts, the following components that make up the structure of the information space can be distinguished:

- the audience that can perceive information transmitted through communication channels;
- developed and improved system of communication technologies (information and telecommunication infrastructure);
- international cooperation system at the information and technological level.

In cyberspace, individuals can communicate with each other, exchange ideas, exchange information, provide social support, conduct business, coordinate activities, create artistic media, play games, participate in political

debates, and so on, using this global network. They are sometimes also called cybernauts. The term cyberspace has become a common tool to describe anything related to the Internet and the various Internet cultures. It is believed that there are common rules and a code of ethics among individuals in cyberspace that are mutually beneficial to all, which is called cyber ethics. Many consider the right to privacy to be the most important feature of a functional code of cyberspace. Such ethical responsibility and aesthetic culture are increasingly embedded in global networks, especially as opinions are linked to online social interactions, and they are evolving alongside different aesthetic approaches in cyberspace.

As Chip Morning and Randall Farmer have argued, cyberspace is characterized by social interactions rather than technical implementations. In cyberspace, the means of communication are considered to be the multiplication of communication channels between real people. The main feature of cyberspace is that it offers an aesthetic environment that can arouse the emotions of individuals, consisting of many participants who have the ability to influence and connect with each other. They derive this concept from observing people's pursuit of richness, complexity, and depth in the virtual world within the realm of aesthetic meaning.

Certain forms of mass media and their cultural manifestations have "aesthetic" characteristics that distinguish them from other types of expression. Critics such as John Ellis have sought to define the aesthetics of television itself, using the concept of digital aesthetics to distinguish the medium from other media such as radio, film, and video. "Digital Aesthetics" explained how the digital representation of the world is presented and aesthetically different from the analog one. It provided extensive information about the digital landscape and offered insights into how digital culture has transformed our professional and personal lives. It examined the textual dynamics and characteristics of digital technology in more detail and explored its form.

The main features of digital media The nature of these devices is such that they are controlled by precise, discrete electrical pulses, usually described as "on" and "off." Thus, the general aesthetic of digital devices is that these wires are tangled, and indeed some manufacturers are experimenting with "smart electricity," which would provide network services through every outlet in a home or office. Wireless networks and the digital companion Other applications, such as television, are transmitted over the air and are effectively invisible, inaudible, and untouchable. This brings up the first problem with digital

aesthetics, which is that many aspects of digital media are simply not perceptible. In fact, what individuals cannot see is often the most important factor in digital aesthetics. However, digital media usually requires some kind of physical device to support it. They are usually likened to small televisions with a typewriter in front of them.

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